

APPLICATION OF HYDROGEL ENHANCING THE FIELD CROP PRODUCTION: A REVIEW

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Abstract

In arid and semiarid region water are most limiting factor that hinder the crop production. The super absorbent polymer having capacity to absorb water from the moist soil. It is new technique to water management under the stressed condition to conserve the soil moisture near the crop zone by reducing evaporation, deep percolation, and runoff losses. Agricultural hydrogel are water absorbing granules which swell their original size and store huge amount of water and release it back to soil for mitigating crop water demand at time when the crop rhizosphere zones dries up under drought condition. It can play many roles in agriculture including soil water retainer, nutrient and pesticides carrier, seed coating material and soil erosion reducer etc. it can improve the soil physiochemical, hydrophysical and biological properties of soil and decreasing the frequency of irrigation. Hydrogel can improve the water and nutrient use efficiency and boosting the yield and quality of the crops. It is biodegradable materials are non-toxic to soil, crop and environment. Hence, the application of hydrogel polymer will be feasible technological tool which boost the crop production in water deficit areas.

Keywords: Arid and semi-arid, Drought, Hydrogel, Production and Water.

Introduction

Water resources are under a stress to rising global water demand and the combined effects of climate change, which are causing water shortages in arid and semi-arid regions of the world, among other countries. More than two-thirds of the world's freshwater use is accounted by the agricultural, industrial, and urban sectors, therefore there is competition among these industries for the limited amount of water that is available (Oladosu *et al.* 2019). The main abiotic stresses (temperature, salinity, and drought) that have an impact on agricultural production are anticipated to get worse as a result of urbanization and land degradation. Similar to this, irrigation water is getting harder to find, thus people are looking for more advance agricultural methods that encourage efficient water use (Calcagnile *et al.* 2019). More than 70% of freshwater on a global scale is used for agriculture, but by 2050, there will need to be a 50% increase in agricultural productivity and a 15% rise in water demand in order to feed a population of nearly nine billion people. Among other things, issues like expanding food consumption and declining water supplies are posing an increasing danger to food security (Kreye *et al.* 2009). Water is one of the most limiting factor which effect the agriculture production. Researching and developing new materials for water management and with long viability. There are lot of scope in Developing biodegradable hydrogels for use in commercial agricultural which improve water efficiency and helping in environmental preservation.

Under drought conditions, the hydrogel polymer has a high capacity to absorb huge amounts of water and hold onto it for a considerable amount of time; polymers could absorb and preserve a quantity of water many times their weight, reducing water loss and extending irrigation intervals, and implementing some soil physical features (Montesano *et al.* 2015). The hydrogel polymer is used in the agricultural industry for a number of purposes, including water storage, seed coating, reducing soil erosion, food additives, tissue culture, and as structural materials (producing mulches) (Yang *et al.* 2002). Earlier studies suggested that the soil's physical qualities, such as aeration and the rate of agglomeration and fusion between soil particles, may be implemented by the application of low quantities of Super absorb polymer (SAP) by 0.001% (Wallace *et al.* 1986). Hence, applying hydrogel may be a suitable method to improve the usage of fertilizers and water in arid areas. The purpose of this paper is to discuss the use of hydrogel polymers in the agricultural industry in the Arabian region and their various uses to enhance plant development, boost yields overall, and enhance fruit quality.

Hydrogel

Chemical polymerization techniques are typically used to produce synthetic-based hydrogels (Ahmed 2013) Bio-based hydrogels come from natural sources, as was previously said, and many techniques have been used to produce bio-based polymers. As an example, microorganisms can produce polyhydroxyalkanoates by fermentation, while biotechnology techniques can produce poly lactides and poly(butylene succinate) Babu *et al.* 2013). Charles Goodyear first proposed the concept of polymer crosslinking in 1839 with the goal of making sulfur crosslinked rubber more durable and long-lasting than uncrosslinked rubber (Mane *et al.* 2016).

New strategies have to be adopted to mitigate the ill effects of drought. One such novel approach is thought to be use of hydrogels in agriculture. Hydrogels are superabsorbent polymers (SAPs) which on an average, hold 332- 465 times water of its weight and release it slowly in drought stress conditions in light soils (Dehkordi 2016). Hydrogels are prone to swelling and retaining a significant amount of water or deflating and losing their moisture because of their three-dimensional, cross-connected hydrophilic polymer networks. They serve as tiny reservoirs as a results (Ahmed 2015). The Hydrogel polymer is an inert substance that affects the physical characteristics of soil, such as its ability to store water, its aggregate, and its permeability, as well as its density, structure, and texture (Abd El-Wahed *et al.* 2013) Hydrogel is now given to natural polysaccharide polymers over synthetic polymers because of controlled release systems, safety to the environment, cost-effectiveness, easy accessibility, and biodegradability (Ahmed *et al.* 2019)

Application of hydrogel

Hydrogels act as soil conditioners to improve soil structure at higher depths through aggregation, stabilize surface soils to prevent the formation of crusts, increase water-holding capacity, and promote plant growth and development. The soil texture affects how quickly hydrogel is applied in agriculture. It is 2.5 kilogram ha⁻¹ at a soil depth of 6 to 8 inches for clay soil and up to 5.0 kg/ha at a soil depth of 4 inches for sandy soil. Hydrogels can be applied to soil using essentially two different techniques:

(i) Dry technique to subsoil: a dry polymer, such as polyallylamine (PAAm) or polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), is mixed with sandy soil to a depth of 15 to 25 cm, moistening the soil for swelling before cultivation. The soil structure is enhanced, and water penetration and retention capacity are increased once the polymer has inflated.

(ii) Wet method to topsoil: The topsoil is initially wetted, the polymer

solution is sprayed onto it, it is dried for water-stable aggregate stability, and then it is immediately seeded. This wet approach can boost soil hydraulic conductivity, decrease soil erosion, and use less water. The hydrogel can spray with combined with micronutrients and insecticides.

Hydrogel impact on different crop growth and yield

A summary of the positive impacts of various hydrogel treatment levels on crop yields under various soil, crop, and climatic conditions are summarized in Table 1. According to the experimental findings, the increase in yield brought about by the addition of a hydrogel was reported to be 11.0-27.8% for sunflower, 14.8-51.3% for wheat, 6.2% for aerobic rice, 45.0% for soybean, 21.9-23.3% for pearl millet, 5.3% for mustard, and 36.6% for sugar beet. This amply shows that soil application of hydrogel increased the yields of different crops, which may be due to adequate water availability by the polymer and indirect nutrient supply to the plants under moisture stress conditions, which in turn led to adequate translocation of water, nutrients, and photosynthates and ultimately higher economic yield (Abobatta 2018, Yangyuoru *et al.* 2019, Roy *et al.* 2019). Hydrogel treatment increases soil water availability, which helps avoid water stress during prolonged periods of water scarcity. This can reduce the water and nutrient infiltration deep root zone. When the soil is treated with super absorbent polymers, the seed germination, seedling emergence, and the vigor, stability of plant growth, and yield can be ensured under drought stress (Ali *et al.* 2014 and Montesano *et al.* 2015). According to (Austin 1992) adding hydrogel to soil, peat moss, or pine bark did not enhance plant growth, yield, or berry weight. Adding hydrogel to organic matter for soil amendments had little to no economic benefit; on the contrary, it might pose a life-threatening risk to young blueberry plants. Similarly, (Meena *et al.* 2015) found no increase in wheat yield after using hydrogel. Notwithstanding these drawbacks, hydrogel is still thought of as a low-cost alternative water management technology that contributes to the creation of a supportive environment for the enhancement of the effectiveness of soil and water management in agriculture.

Conclusion

In dry and semiarid areas, water is now the most limiting factor to crop production. The use of hydrogel as a soil conditioner can increase the soil's ability to retain and release water, increase irrigation efficiency and nutrient use effectiveness, improve crop production and quality, and maintain environmental quality. In terms of enhanced yield, this hydrogel technology could become a revolutionary and practically useful technology in water-stressed locations (cereals, vegetables, oilseeds, flowers, spices, plantation, etc.). According to this review, the widespread deployment of hydrogel could benefit farmers and other stakeholders by optimizing water resource management for greater agricultural productivity.

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Table-1. Significant impact of hydrogel on field crops.

Year and season	Soil texture	Test crop	Variety	Condition	Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	Yield increase over without hydrogel (%)	Reference
2015-16 (Kharif)	-	Sunflower		Rainfed	Pusa hydrogel at 2.5 kg/ha	1.65	33.0	Kumar <i>et al.</i> (2020)
2003 (Spring & summer)	Silty loam	Soybean	Cultivar L1	Drought stress	Tarawat A 200 hydrogel at 225 kg/ha	6.42	45.0	Yazdani <i>et al.</i> (2007)
2006-08 (Kharif)	Sandy loam	Pearl millet	ICMH- 356	Arid	Seed coating 20 g hydrogel +thiourea (0.1%)+DMSO (0.01%)/ kg seed	2.21	23.3	Singh (2012)
2015 & 2016 (Summer)	Loamy sand	Pearl millet	Gujarat hybrid Bajara 732	Semiarid and subtropical	Hydrogel at 5.0 kg/ha	4.49	21.9	Saini <i>et al.</i> (2020)
2014-16 (Rabi)	Sandy loam	Mustard	NRCDR 2	Temperate	Hydrogel at 2.5 kg/ha	1.27	5.3	Bharat <i>et al.</i> (2019)
2013-14	Sandy	Sugar beet	Baraka	Arid	Hydrogel at 40 kg/ha	80.0	36.6	l-Karamany <i>et al.</i> (2015)
2015-16 (Kharif)	-	Sunflower		Rainfed	100% RDF (80 : 60 : 30 kg NPK ha ¹)+hydrogel at 2.5 kg/ha in seed furrows	1.24	27.8	Gaikwad <i>et al.</i> (2017)
2016-17 (Kharif)	-	Castor		Rainfed	100% RDF (80 : 60 : 30 kg NPK ha ¹)+hydrogel at 5 kg/ha	1.76	30	Kumar <i>et al</i> (2020)
2014-17 (Kharif)	-	Sunflower		Rainfed	100% RDF (80 : 60 : 30 kg NPK ha ¹)+hydrogel at 2.5 kg/ha in seed furrows	1.26	11.0	Ghatol <i>et al.</i> (2018)
2012-14 (Rabi)	Sandy loam	Wheat HD 2733	Wheat HD 2733	Subtropical semiarid	Two types of irrigation at tillering and flowering with hydrogel at 2.5 kg/ha	3.31	14.9 (w.r.t. two types of irrigation at tillering and flowering)	Singh <i>et al.</i> (2020)
2012-13	Clayey	Wheat	AKAW-4627		100% NPK +hydrogel at 5.0 kg/ ha	2.51	18.3	Mahla <i>et al.</i> (2017)
2009 (Kharif)	Sandy loam	Aerobic rice	Super basmati		Hydrogel at 2.5 kg/ ha	2.39	6.2	Rehman <i>et al.</i> (2011)